

EDUCATOR'S CHRONICLE

Dr. B. M. Vidyavathi*, N. V. Pooja, D. M. Aishwarya**,
J. Pravallika** & Srinivasan****

* Department of CSE, Ballari Institute of Technology and Management, Ballari, Karnataka

** Department of ISE, Ballari Institute of Technology and Management,
Ballari, Karnataka

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Abstract:

In recent times organizations and higher educational institutions maintain record of events of individual to keep track of the individual performance. This helps in awarding appraisal, analysis of competence of individuals and also in motivating faculty to improve their performance. In the existing system the task is done individually in own format which is strenuous to analyze and maintain up to date which leads to unavailability of data when needed. In this work we have designed and developed an automated report generation system that maintains record of events, which when required can be updated and automatic report can be generated. Accessing of data is fast and accurate thus performance of the system is improved.

Key Words: Academic Data, String Matching Algorithm, Data Analysis & Clustering Prediction

1. Introduction:

Automated report generation system provides a simple interface for maintaining the faculty information. It can be used by educational institutes to keep track of the individual performance of faculty information and their academic activities. Achieving this objective is difficult using a manual system as the information is scattered. This system focuses on presenting information in an easy and intelligible manner which provides online registration and profile creation. It is designed to reduce the paper resource, manual calculations and risk to human operators. Hence it is reliable, accurate and faster in access.

Design and implementation of this web based automated report generation system replaces the traditional manual documentation of reports. It also helps to maintain up to date data by providing the online interface to faculty. Here, the admin can directly access all the aspects of the faculty's information and their academic activities through a secure online interface. All data is stored in the server which provides the highest possible level of security.

The system features ensure conformity to data access. It increases the efficiency and performance of record management thereby decreasing the work hours needed to access.

2. Literature Review:

All researchers have aimed to develop and provide an automated report generation system to monitor the various works that are carried out by a educational institutions. They provided up to date information of the system which improved efficiency of college record management and decrease the space between faculty and college. The major contributions to this topic are summarized below:

Nilesh V. K. Nerkar, Nilakshi Jain, Dhruvin Mehta, Kuldeep Sodha, Chetan Barot in [1] [4] proposed this system to monitor student and faculty Information which deals all kind of student details, academic related reports, college details, course details, curriculum, batch details, placement details, assignment list, syllabus, lesson plans, test papers and experiment lists. It tracks all the details of a student from the day one to the end of the course which can be used for reporting purpose, tracking of attendance, progress in the course, completed semesters, years, final exam result and all these will be available through a secure, online interface embedded in the college's website. It will also have faculty details, batch execution details, students' details, the various academic notifications to the staff and students updated by the college administration.

S. R. Bharamagoudar, Geeta R.B., S. G. Totad in [2] proposed this system to keep track of student information. It is used by educational institutes to maintain the records of students easily. Student information system deals with all kind of student details, academic related reports, college details, course details, curriculum, batch details, placement details and other resource related details too. It tracks all the details of a student from the day one to the end of the course which can be used for all reporting purpose, tracking of attendance, progress in the course, completed semesters, years, coming semester year curriculum details, exam details, project or any other assignment details, final exam result and all these will be available through a secure, online interface embedded in the college's website. It will also have faculty details, batch execution details, students' details in all aspects, the various academic notifications to the staff and students updated by the college administration.

Ghemud Rahul Dhanaji , Shendkar Akshay Ssambhaji , Lahor Ankit Sunil , Kendre Anjali Giridhari, Prof. Rokade M.R. [3] [5] introduce the environment for faculties to handle their work and maintain record easily instead of making a lot of paper work. This is achieved by mobile application. Mobile application provides the platform for the faculties to overcome such issues and complex work. This mobile application is platform independent workspace for faculties so that they can access or use it with ease form no location

dependency. It supports all types of platforms like android, iOS, windows etc. Providing a mobile application is again a huge achievement so that faculties can take a view to their work while they are on move. Faculties can easily interact with the students directly so that each time there is no need to inform each student. Better secure transfer of the all information provided using latest technologies. Updating, Inserting, and all the operations can be done easily and efficiently.

Our system introduce a environment for faculties to maintain record easily instead of making a lot of paper work. It is a web based application which automates the existing system where maintaining faculty academic details and profile details are maintained manually. The information can be updated and accessed easily.

3. Existing System Vs Proposed System:

In the existing system we require more man power. The manual data entry is time consuming task and also requires large volume of paper work and heavy manual calculations. To avoid all these limitations and make the working more accurate the system needs to be automated. The proposed system is designed to reduce the paper resource and manual calculations. This can be used in educational institutions to know all the achievements done by faculties.

The existing system has more workload for the authorized person, but in the case of Proposed System, the user can register through the portal and data can be entered to the system in specified format.

The aim of proposed system is to develop a system of improved facilities. The proposed system can overcome all the limitations of the existing system. The existing system has several disadvantages and difficulties to work well. The proposed system tries to eliminate these difficulties. The proposed system will help the user to reduce the workload as well as heavy documentation.

The Proposed System has got the Following Features:

- ✓ Minimize manual data entry.
- ✓ Minimizes heavy documentation.
- ✓ Greater efficiency.
- ✓ Better service.
- ✓ User friendliness.
- ✓ Minimum time required.

Figure 1: Block diagram of Educator's Chronicle

The user login to the system, add their individual credits as well as update them. Based on their requirement parameters like year wise, category type clustering of data is done. The data input given by the faculty, performance of the individual as well as organisational improvement is analysed. On analysis of data individual faculty appraisal can be rewarded. The user can generate reports of their academic achievements in a click.

4. Results and Discussion:

Figure 2: The registration include following credentials

The faculty should initially register in the web application in order to login. Fig 2 shows the credentials that should be provided by the faculty. The admin will approve the registration so that fake entries are not done. The admin and faculty should provide their username and password for logging in to application. The faculty can update their profile when needed. In order to add their achievements faculty should go for create page. Fig 3 shows the credentials that should be provided by faculty to add their achievements. If the faculty wants to view their achievements they can go for view or search option for viewing any particular achievements as shown in fig 4. The delete option is provided for admin to remove faculty if they have left the institution this is shown in fig 5. The admin has a search option, he can search results by faculty, year wise, category type and can take print of these reports as shown fig 6.

Figure 3: Create option for adding faculties achievements

Figure 4: Search option to view any particular achievements

Figure 5: Faculty entries can be viewed by admin

Figure 6: Search option for viewing any particular results

5. Conclusion:

The proposed system have been designed and developed as a web based application to keep track of faculties' academic details and helps in rewarding appraisal of faculty. This kind of system also brings impulse in achieving goals and develops competence in the organization. The system reduces the burden in maintaining bulk academic records, in an educational institution. It also facilitates the ease of managing details of faculties in contrast to the manual collection and storage of gigantic intellectual data. Generating reports is also a trouble-free job which can effortlessly comprehensible.

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